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Advancing Soil Compaction Assessment: A Comprehensive Study in Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Soil degradation is a substantial threat to agricultural productivity and ecosystem service provision across Europe. However, the nature of soil degradation varies across spatial scales, with considerable regional disparities observed amongst individual member states. In Ireland, soil compaction represents a significant soil threat, imposed by the country's environmental conditions, inherent soil characteristics and prevailing land management practices. Despite being a widely recognised issue, this study presents the first Indicative Soil Compaction map for Ireland. The map helps to inform strategic management practices to mitigate soil compaction at regional scales. We utilise a dual indicator approach, with soil bulk density serving as an indicator of compaction and soil moisture deficit and trafficable days as an indicator of environmental conditions. This integrated approach provides an assessment of soil compaction at soil association level. Our findings reveal that compaction is high in Ireland, although its degree varies geographically across the country, influenced by management practices and intrinsic soil properties. High bulk density soils are found to dominate the country, particularly in the east and southeast of Ireland, indicating a high degree of soil compaction. Whilst much of central Ireland is characterised by moderate compaction, it is imperative to implement good management practices in both moderate and high bulk density soils to prevent further compaction. It is evident that management practices (e.g., intensive arable farming) have a potentially overriding effect compared to intrinsic soil susceptibility to compaction, which is apparent across the southeast of Ireland. This research now provides a valuable tool for developing targeted regional strategies to manage and reduce soil compaction, aligning with broader European Union ambitions to achieve healthy soils by the year 2050.

1 | Introduction

According to the Mission Board for Soil Health and Food, 60%–70% of soils in the European Union (EU) are degraded due to unsustainable management practices (Veerman et al. 2020). Soil degradation has been linked with severe environmental and socio-economic consequences, including decreased agricultural productivity, food insecurity, reduced carbon sequestration, loss of biodiversity, environmental degradation, economic vulnerability and social and political instability (Barbut and

Alexander 2016). Healthy soils are critical to deliver a range of ecosystem services to benefit people, including public goods related to the wider ecosystem functioning and societal well-being (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, (MEA) 2005; Haines-Young and Potschin 2018). However, such high levels of soil degradation undermine not only the delivery of food, fuel, feed and fibre but also impede key soil functions to deliver ecosystem services (Haygarth and Ritz 2009; Schulte et al. 2014; Vogel et al. 2018). Whilst the EU recognises eight main threats to soil, such as erosion, organic matter loss, soil contamination, soil

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Summary

- This research provides the first countrywide assessment of soil compaction in Ireland.
- Compaction is a key threat to Ireland's soils, requiring novel information to develop solutions.
- Degree and distribution of soil compaction vary across soil moisture and management regimes.
- Targeted management strategies will be essential for mitigating soil compaction in Ireland.

sealing, salinisation, floods and landslides and decline in biodiversity, soil compaction is a key threat worldwide (European Commission (EC) 2006; Creamer et al. 2010; Frene et al. 2024).

Globally, an estimated 20% of the cropland area is considered at high risk of subsoil compaction, concentrated in highly mechanised regions (Keller and Or 2022). In Europe, soil compaction is estimated to affect 33 million hectares (Ha) of land (Hamza and Anderson 2005). European and national scale studies have investigated and mapped soil compaction, such as the Natural Susceptibility to Compaction map released in 2008 by the European Commission. That map uses soil data from the European Soil Database v2 combined with the CORINE Land Cover 2000 dataset. At a scale of 1:1 million, the soil coverage and diversity presented is a simplified representation of reality; however, its utility rests in being the only harmonised soil database at European scale based on a participatory approach with experts from all countries (Panagos et al. 2022). National examples exist, such as for France, but are limited to arable soils (Richer-De-Forges et al. 2024) or a partial topsoil compaction risk map of Scotland (Lilly and Baggaley 2018). The European Soil Bureau Network recommended and endorsed the preparation of a georeferenced soil database for Europe at a scale of 1:250,000, considered a feasible scale for national scale assessments that would simultaneously facilitate intercountry comparisons related to soils and sustainability (Dudal et al. 1993). This is necessary to support EU Member States to transition towards pan-European targets that are to be achieved by 2050. Equally, the contextual nature of soil compaction means that national and subnational targeting is a requirement to facilitate more nuanced pathways in favour of sustainable land management.

Soil compaction can occur naturally, with a soil's susceptibility influenced by factors such as soil properties and weather conditions. However, soil compaction also occurs in response to mechanised agriculture, with higher vehicle weights associated with an increased risk of subsoil compaction (Kumar et al. 2018; Keller and Or 2022; Mileusnić et al. 2022). Literature has traditionally focused on compaction in arable systems (Radford et al. 2001; Nevens and Reheul 2003; Koch et al. 2008), but more recently, research has also addressed compaction in grassland systems caused by heavy trafficking in suboptimal conditions (Vero et al. 2014; Emmet-Booth et al. 2020; Bondi et al. 2021; Lepore et al. 2024). Whilst the success of modern agriculture in relation to food production has benefitted from the increased capacity of farm machinery, continued success is now undermined by soil compaction that threatens agricultural productivity and

ecological functioning (Hamza and Anderson 2005; Schjønning et al. 2015; Keller and Or 2022). Soil compaction is characterised by increased soil density and reduced pore space between soil particles and soil macropores, giving rise to cascading effects on water transport, root growth and nutrient availability (DeJong-Hughes et al. 2001; Ball et al. 2007; Schjønning et al. 2016; Keller et al. 2017; Frene et al. 2024). It reduces microbial space for nutrient cycling and nutrient availability under low oxygen conditions, increases resistance to root penetration, decreases hydraulic conductivity and air flow and ultimately restricts plant growth and crop yield (Greacen and Sands 1980; Hillel 1980; Soane and Van Ouwwerkerk 1994; Schjønning et al. 2016; Bondi et al. 2021; Frene et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024).

Whilst several studies highlight a negative impact of soil compaction on crop yields (e.g., Schjønning et al. 2016), some research has shown a yield increase with a slight level of compaction (Lindemann et al. 1982). As such, the impact on plant root systems and crop production is not fully disentangled (Konôpka et al. 2008). Overall, soil compaction is highly variable, may affect surface or subsoil and can be of different origins with different levels of impact. This implies that targeted management of agricultural soils is necessary to minimise soil compaction and its negative impacts on soils functioning for yield and other important ecosystem services. Once soil has been compacted, it may take over a decade to return to its original state without intervention, depending on its intrinsic characteristics including its mineralogical composition (Jourgholami et al. 2019).

Compaction has been reported to cause a preferential loss of macropores, which are critical for air and water movement within the soil profile. This is particularly significant due to their essential role in soil ecological functions, including water transmission and storage (Ball 1986; Berisso et al. 2012; Dorner et al. 2010; Matthews et al. 2010). Water provisioning and regulating services are reduced due to changes in the pore network as well as altered capacity for water supply due to changes in hydrological control (Gregory et al. 2006; Haygarth and Ritz 2009; Schulte et al. 2018).

This makes soil water content one of the most critical elements driving the vulnerability of a soil to compaction (Van der Watt 1969). High soil moisture levels increase compaction risk by reducing macropore spaces and diminishing the soil's ability to resist pressure without altering its density (Mitchell and Berry 2001; Lipiec and Hatano 2003). Wet weather conditions exacerbate this risk, as elevated moisture levels weaken soil structure and make it more prone to deformation under pressure. Hamza and Anderson (2005) note that the potential for compaction rises with increasing soil moisture up to field capacity (FC). Consequently, soil moisture at the time of machinery traffic significantly affects the degree of compaction from vehicle-soil interactions (Voorhees and Walker 1977; Meek et al. 1992; Earl 1997; Alakukku et al. 2003; Mari et al. 2008; Bondi et al. 2021). Conversely, excessively dry conditions can also increase compaction, as tightly packed soil particles reduce structural resilience (Shaxson and Barber 2003). Degraded soils, characterised by high bulk density (BD), low porosity and poor structure, are particularly vulnerable to compaction under adverse climatic conditions, leading to further degradation (Pereira et al. 2007). The variability of soil compaction across spatial scales is shaped by

climatic regimes, environmental factors and management practices. Therefore, accurate assessments of soil compaction must consider the interplay of factors like intrinsic soil properties and prevailing climatic conditions (Reichert et al. 2018).

In this context, the Republic of Ireland encompasses diverse soil types, environmental conditions and land management practices, where the delicate balance between environmental protection and the demands of the grass-fed livestock sector necessitates customised management solutions (Casey and Holden 2006; Schulte et al. 2014). Despite the significance of soil compaction and its challenges in Irish soils (Creamer et al. 2010; Bondi et al. 2021; Lepore et al. 2024), a national soil compaction assessment map is currently lacking. Such evaluation is crucial for transitioning towards sustainable land management and agricultural practices, in line with European ambitions, such as the European Green Deal as well as other national policies.

In this research, we aim to develop an Indicative National Soil Compaction Assessment Map to identify compacted areas in Ireland taking an integrated approach that accounts for both inherent soil properties and climatic conditions. Whilst we did not directly measure trafficking pressure across Ireland, some regions are known to experience more intensive management (Central Statistics Office 2021). We assumed that, where trafficking intensity and soil characteristics are similar, weather conditions at the time of trafficking may influence the degree of compaction. We consider soil BD as a measure of soil porosity and an indicator of soil compaction (Campbell 1994; Håkansson and Lipiec 2000; Nawaz et al. 2013). We also accounted for soil moisture deficit (SMD) which is used as an indicator of soil wetness within 30 cm depth based upon 104 climatic weather stations to account for climatic variations (Schulte et al. 2015).

We hypothesise that soil compaction will vary across different climatic conditions and soil types and that soil compaction will be higher in areas where poorly draining soils, above-average rainfall and intensive agricultural practices co-occur, as these conditions collectively limit the soil's capacity to recover and maintain its structural integrity. We address the following research questions:

- Does above-average rainfall exacerbate soil saturation, making it more prone to compaction?
- Do more intensive agricultural practices reflect accelerated soil degradation and compaction status?
- Does the combination of poorly draining soils, high rainfall and intensive agricultural activities create a compounded effect, significantly heightening the overall soil compaction?

The Indicative National Soil Compaction Assessment Map will provide valuable insights into the distribution and primary drivers of soil compaction, facilitating targeted soil management strategies that are country or region specific. Identifying regions most vulnerable to compaction will enable the implementation of tailored interventions for sustainable soil management, thereby contributing to the long-term viability of Ireland's diverse agricultural landscape and overall agricultural sector. Such targeted actions are essential to meet overall EU policy objectives and achieve healthy soils across the EU.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Study Area

Ireland is located to the northwest of mainland Europe, bordered by the Atlantic Ocean to the west and the Irish Sea to the east, making it the westernmost member of the EU (Figure 1). Ireland's total terrestrial land area is approximately 7 million Ha, of which 4.5 million Ha is devoted to agricultural land use (Central Statistics Office 2021). The mean annual air temperature from 1991 to 2020 was 9.8°C, ranging from 8.5°C to 10.8°C. Summer is the warmest season on average (14.6°C) and winter the coolest (5.4°C) (Met Éireann 2023). Due to the moderating influence of the sea, areas closest to the coast are generally the warmest, whilst areas at higher elevations are the coolest (Met Éireann 2023). Nationally, the annual average rainfall over the period 1991–2020 was 1288 mm, although rainfall levels show high variance across local and regional scales and across seasons (Figure 2). The 30-year annual rainfall average distribution shows a typical west to east decline, with the highest rainfall observed in the west of the country, particularly on higher ground (Figure 2). Annual average rainfall ranges from 878 mm along the east coast to 2044 mm in southwest mountainous regions (Met Éireann 2023). The main great soil groups in Ireland include Ombrotrophic peat, Minerotrophic peat, Rendzina, Lithosol, Alluvial, Groundwater Gley, Surface-water Gley, Podzol, Brown Podzolic, Luvisol and Brown Earth (Creamer et al. 2014). For a comparison of these soil groups to the World Reference Base soil classification system, see Reidy et al. (2016). Schulte et al. (2015) classified Irish soils into five drainage categories, being (1) excessively drained, (2) well drained, (3) moderately drained, (4) imperfectly drained and (5) poorly drained.

2.2 | Soil Compaction Indicators: Soil Bulk Density (BD)

The soil BD values utilised in this study were sourced from the Irish Soil Information System National Soil Map of Ireland (Irish SIS) project, established in 2008. This dataset includes both measured BD values and estimates derived from pedo-transfer functions (PTFs) for points where direct measurements were not taken. Direct measurements were obtained from undisturbed samples collected from representative soil profiles, following the methodology outlined by Jones et al. (2003). To estimate soil BD for unsampled locations, PTFs derived from international datasets were used with measured soil properties. See Hollis et al. (2012) for an evaluation of PTF performance across various European soils. These functions were initially applied and then validated, with the best performing PTF selected, enabling the application of PTF derived BD values where those were not directly measured. Details of this methodology can be found in Reidy et al. (2016).

Soil BD values were categorised into three groups based on the classification by Bondi et al. (2018). These were: BD 1, representing a group of soils with low BD (< 1.0 g cm⁻³); BD 2, indicative of moderate BD (ranging between 1.0 and 1.4 g cm⁻³); and BD 3, indicating high BD (> 1.4 g cm⁻³). The 3rd Edition Soils map masked regions associated with peat, urban, rock, water body, tidal, salt marsh and islands that were not analysed in this

FIGURE 1 | Study area: (A) location of Ireland within Europe and (B) map of Ireland.

research and thus were classified as ‘Data unavailable’. QGIS 3.30.0-’s-Hertogenbosch was used to generate a spatial distribution map of soil BD (Figure 3).

2.3 | Soil Moisture Deficit (SMD)

SMD, defined as the amount of rainfall required to raise soil moisture to FC (Clark 2002), serves as a valuable index of climatic conditions affecting soil moisture status (Jones and Thomasson 1985). FC refers to the maximum amount of water that soil can retain after excess water has drained. SMD is zero when soils is at FC (SMD = 0), negative when current soil moisture exceeds FC (SMD < 0), meaning the soil cannot absorb additional water, and positive when the soil moisture is below FC (SMD > 0), indicating the soil can still absorb more water before reaching FC (Seneviratne et al. 2010). Conversely, throughout this paper, ‘SMD < 0 mm’ refers to wet soil conditions and ‘SMD > 0 mm’ refers to dry soil conditions. In consequence, the number of days when soils were considered untrafficable were determined based on the FC point, when SMD values were < 0 mm. These identified conditions when soil was more susceptible to compaction by machinery or trampling of livestock (Batey 2009). Data for daily SMD over a 30-year period from 1979 to 2008, for 104 climatic weather stations operated by Met Éireann, were used (O’Sullivan et al. 2015). The daily SMD was calculated for excessively drained, well-drained, moderately drained, imperfectly drained and poorly drained soils following the drainage classification by Schulte et al. (2015). The principal soil series of each soil association were categorised into drainage classes based on a set of diagnostic criteria and rules primarily linked with ‘gleyic’ and ‘stagnic’ features (Schulte et al. 2015). For example, the presence of mottling within 40 cm, with an argic/spodic horizon causing stagnation was assigned

to the poorly drained class. The ‘excessively drained’ and ‘well drained’ classes were conjoined as one into the well-drained class due to their comparable dynamics, which are identical during winter months (Schulte et al. 2015). Excessively drained soils represents a very limited area of < 20,000 ha, primarily in the southeast of Ireland.

In this study, we especially focused on wet conditions that represent periods of greatest concern for soil trafficability. We categorised these conditions into groups based on the number of untrafficable days (in 10-day intervals), as shown in Table 1. Hereafter, SMD groups correspond to groups of days during which the soil was untrafficable. It is important to note that SMD groups 1–5 were not observed within the study area. To generate a thematic indicative SMD groups map, SMD values were interpolated using Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) (Mueller et al. 2004) using QGIS 3.30.0-’s-Hertogenbosch to enable a detailed analysis of trafficability patterns. The maximum number of untrafficable days was observed in SMD group 29 (280–290 days).

2.4 | Combination of SMD and BD

Soil BD was combined with SMD groups to enable an analysis of soil compaction by integrating both soil physical properties and climatic factors. The Irish SIS polygons were assigned to a SMD class based on their respective drainage classifications, facilitating an analysis of spatial variability at the soil association level. The drainage categories within the Irish SIS were assigned based on diagnostic features identified through field-based descriptions. Subsequently, a comprehensive spatial dataset incorporating both BD and SMD groups was created using QGIS through intersection analysis to generate the final shapefile indicative of the soil compaction map (Figure 4).

FIGURE 2 | Ireland's rainfall average over the period 1991–2020 for Winter, Spring, Summer and Autumn. Sourced from Met Éireann (2023).

3 | Results

3.1 | Preliminary Soil Properties Analysis

The analysis indicated that BD data ranged from 0.89 to 1.67 gcm^{-3} across all soil drainage classes. Untrafficable days ranged from 53 to 178 for SMD-well drained soils, 106 to 235 for SMD-moderately drained soils, 132–264 for imperfectly drained soils, and 158–291 for SMD-poorly drained soils (Table 2). The lowest coefficient of variation (CV) was observed in poorly drained soils, whilst the highest CV was in well-drained soils, respectively. According to Wilding's (1985) soil variability assessment criteria, SMD-well drained soils exhibited moderate variability, whilst the remaining classes and BD had low variability.

3.2 | Climatic Context of Compaction

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of BD across Ireland. The spatial distribution of BD shows that approximately 2.16 million

Ha corresponds to the soil BD group 3, followed by BD group 2, accounting for an approximate area of 1.62 million Ha. BD group 1 was mainly confined to the eastern region of Ireland around the Wicklow Mountains and amongst other Mountainous areas of Leinster, encompassing just 93,000 Ha. Therefore, the largest percentage of the area examined falls into BD group 3, representing an area over 30% larger than BD group 2, indicating that a significant proportion of Irish soils already have a degree of compaction.

Soil compaction is influenced by moisture conditions and climatic wetness estimates (Jones et al. 2003). The soil BD map was overlain with the climatic data. By examining the co-occurrence of the SMD group and BD, we aimed to highlight areas where persistent soil wetness might contribute to compaction, particularly with soils are trafficked under such conditions. Figure 4 presents the spatial distribution of the classified BD and SMD group (BD-SMD) data across Ireland, highlighting patterns associated with combined soil and climatic characteristics.

FIGURE 3 | Spatial distribution of BD groups of agricultural soils derived from Bondi et al. (2018) classification applied to Irish SIS (Creamer et al. 2014).

TABLE 1 | Number of untrafficable days for different SMD groups.

SMD group	Number of untrafficable days	SMD group	Number of untrafficable days
1	0–10	16	150–160
2	10–20	17	160–170
3	20–30	18	170–180
4	30–40	19	180–190
5	40–50	20	190–200
6	50–60	21	200–210
7	60–70	22	210–220
8	70–80	23	220–230
9	80–90	24	230–240
10	90–100	25	240–250
11	100–110	26	250–260
12	110–120	27	260–270
13	120–130	28	270–280
14	130–140	29	280–290
15	140–150	End	

3.2.1 | Low BD Across SMD Groups

Soils with the lowest BD are predominantly located in a confined region in the east of Ireland, particularly around the Wicklow Mountains, the Cooley Mountains in County Louth and Mount Leinster in County Carlow (Figure 5A). Additionally, pockets of BD1-SMD soils were identified along the west coast, especially in the northwest region, although these occurrences are limited. These areas of low BD across SMD groups are mainly associated with mountainous or upland regions and are absent in the southern and midland areas of Ireland. SMD groups spanned from 17 to 27 across BD1, indicating 160–270 days of untraffiability.

3.2.2 | Moderate BD Across SMD Groups

The BD2-SMD classification primarily encompasses the midlands and central fringes of Ireland (Figure 5B). The lowest BD2-SMD values were observed near the eastern border counties of Louth and Monaghan, as well as in eastern Cavan and northern Meath. Additional areas of moderate BD across SMD groups include a distinct region along the Waterford coast. This classification entails a more widespread distribution of moderate BD soils across Ireland compared to the low BD soils. SMD groups in BD2 ranged from 09 to 27, corresponding to 80–270 untrafficable days during the year, with the highest BD2-SMD groupings located towards the south of

FIGURE 4 | Indicative national scale soil compaction map for Ireland based on the Irish SIS at a scale of 1:250,000 and SMD data.

TABLE 2 | Descriptive statistics of soil characteristics and untrafficable days.

Soil characteristics	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	CV (%)	SD
BD (g cm^{-3})	0.89	1.67	1.41	1.44	13.48	0.19
SMD-well drained (days)	53	178	115	113	18.52	21.3
SMD-moderately drained (days)	106	235	174	171	12.53	21.8
SMD-imperfectly drained (days)	132	264	203	201	10.84	22
SMD-poorly drained (days)	158	291	232	230	9.66	22.4

Abbreviations: BD, bulk density; CV, coefficient of variation; SD, standard deviation; SMD, soil moisture deficit untrafficable days.

Ireland, encompassing the highest proportions of untrafficable days.

3.2.3 | High BD Across SMD Groups

The highest BD values are predominantly found in the eastern, south-eastern and southern regions of Ireland, forming a nearly continuous belt of BD3 (Figure 5C). Areas around the south-western regions, Cork and West Kerry, exhibit the SMD groups with the highest values in relation to the number of untrafficable days within the BD3 group. Other SMD classes with high untraffiability within the BD3 classification are more dispersed across the map. SMD groups across BD3 encompass the widest range, spanning 08–29, from as low as 80–90 days to 280–290 days where the soil is untrafficable. This suggests significant

local and regional variations in soil properties, environmental conditions and/or management.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | Compaction Patterns Across Soil Moisture Regimes

4.1.1 | Low BD Within Soil Moisture Regimes

The low BD-SMD identified groups are areas predominantly characterised by peaty soils. These regions are not strictly peat but rather organo-mineral soils that retain agricultural value. These soils have a high organic matter content (Creamer et al. 2014), with studies showing a positive correlation between soil

FIGURE 5 | (A) BD1-SMD grouping, (B) BD2-SMD grouping, (C) BD3-SMD grouping, and (D) SMD groups by the BD category. The areas within the red lines indicate SMD groups, intended as the number of untrafficable days, that overlap amongst all three BD groups.

organic carbon (SOC) and porosity (Fukumasu et al. 2022). Such soils typically exhibit lower BD values (Mobilian and Craft 2022).

The poor drainage characteristics of the BD1 soils may be attributed to a combination of the soil composition and slightly higher rainfall, largely due to their upland distribution, which is evident in Figure 2. The BD1 soils have a lower range of SMD groups, from 17 to 27. This is a much narrower range compared to the BD2 and BD3 soils, probably because low BD is less represented in our soil datasets. These regions align with extensive farming practices, such as the rough grazing of hill sheep, which involves less mechanisation and lower stocking rates (Teagasc 2015; Central Statistics Office 2022). Heavy machinery is often not necessary for such farming systems, whilst stocking rates are far less than conventional (Samuel et al. 2022). The use of these practices reduces the likelihood of machinery-induced soil compaction and poaching by livestock, both of which potentially increase BD.

4.1.2 | Moderate BD Within Soil Moisture Regimes

The soils in areas classified as BD2 across various SMD groups, most common in the central and north-eastern regions of Ireland

(Figure 5B), are primarily composed of Alluvial soil with loamy textures, often associated with an organic horizon. These soils, characterised by a balance of sand, silt and clay, provide a structure that supports both effective water retention and drainage, crucial for maintaining optimal soil moisture levels. Such properties confer resilience to these soils, making them less susceptible to extreme weather conditions, such as heavy rainfall and saturation, compared to areas with BD3 soils. Organo-mineral soils found in the BD2-SMD cohort are rich in organic matter, which enhances soil structure and resilience to compaction, contributing to improved water retention whilst facilitating adequate drainage and reducing the risk of waterlogging. This moderate drainage capacity generally ensures efficient management of water infiltration and retention, mitigating excessive dryness and water saturation.

4.1.3 | High BD Within Soil Moisture Regimes

High BD soils exhibit the broadest range of SMD groups, indicating that these areas are particularly susceptible to compaction, having the highest number of untrafficable days. This can be intensified by moisture regimes alone or, even more so, when combined with intensive management practices. In the

south-western region of Ireland, particularly in counties like Cork and Kerry, several factors contribute to the elevated soil compaction status. Soils in this part of the country support intensive grassland farming (Central Statistics Office 2021) and are mainly characterised by Surface Water Gleys of poor drainage, higher clay fractions and clayey textures (Creamer et al. 2014). The combination of high annual precipitation, fine-textured soils and management practices whereby highly productive dairy farm systems operate in a context where soils might be untrafficable for up to 290 days per year (Figure 5D). However, adhering to recommended grazing management practices in such conditions has been found to mitigate soil compaction, in particular in order to protect soils that are associated with large carbon stores often found in these areas (Bondi et al. 2021; Tuohy et al. 2021). This finding underscores the importance of both natural and management-related factors on soil compaction in this part of the country. Similar conditions are found also in parts of the north-east, Monaghan and Cavan, where Surface Water Gleys also dominate, resulting in high compaction in these areas (Figure 5C). Although the results are presented at national scale, the granularity of the map can be reflected by the occurrence of areas that have considerable differences in relation to trafficability, even when the same weather regime exists. For example, areas close to the Cork–Kerry region can also exhibit scope for more trafficking, having fewer untrafficable days. These areas feature Humic Brown Earth soils and Podzolics, which entail good to moderate drainage, yet remain susceptible to water-logging and compaction in extreme conditions.

The highest concentration of BD3 values is also found in the eastern, south-eastern and southern regions of Ireland. These areas are dominated by Brown Earth soils, which can be identified by the lowest SMD groups (drier conditions) across BD3 (Figure 5C). These soils exhibit good drainage characteristics and lower clay content and are of predominantly sandy-loam or sandy textures (Creamer et al. 2014). Additionally, the eastern seaboard experiences some of the lowest rainfall levels in the country (Met Éireann 2023). These favourable conditions contribute to intensive agricultural practices and high levels of trafficability throughout the year. Although these types of soils are typically less susceptible to compaction, exhibiting a lower BD due to their larger particle sizes and greater pore spaces, intensive management practices such as frequent tillage can increase BD, thus becoming compacted (Singh et al. 2023). Several studies have highlighted the critical impact of management practices on soil structure (Assefa et al. 2020; Frene et al. 2024). Therefore, intensive management practices have likely been a significant driver of the compacted soils in these regions.

4.2 | Soil Compaction Dynamics Across Ireland

Soil compaction is a function of three main factors: weather conditions, soil properties and management practices. Our research has demonstrated the integrative nature of soil compaction that requires the consideration of all of these factors collectively. Figure 5D illustrates that soils falling within the BD1 class across SMD groups range from SMD groups of 17 to 27. BD2 spans from SMD groups of 09 to 27, whilst BD3 ranges

from SMD groups of 08 to 29. From SMD groups 17 to 27, there is an overlap amongst all BD classes. This suggests that under the same weather conditions and based on SMD groups, the primary factors influencing the soil compaction within the overlap area are management practices and/or soil properties.

From SMD group 17 to 27, where it is indicated that soils are untrafficable up to 270 days annually, certain regions are classified as BD1, others as BD2 and some as BD3 (Figure 5D). Where SMD remains constant across BD categories, the impact of weather on soil compaction is similar; therefore, compaction can be attributed to differences in soil type, management practices or the combination of both. In eastern areas, characterised by high soil quality, lower clay fraction and lighter textures, management practices play a key role in soil compaction. Conversely, in south-western areas, the combination of soil properties and management practices is key to contributing to compaction. Soils within the 03–28 and 03–29 category (over 270 days of untraffiability per year) are almost certainly compacted and may need adapted management practices.

Soils within BD3 span the widest range of SMD groups and represent a greater compaction, though the nature of this intensity varies across regions. Regions with higher SMD groups are exposed to the combined effects of heavier soils with more adverse weather conditions for trafficking. Under this scenario, farmers and managers must pay particular attention to their management practices and mitigation strategies that need to be applied.

4.3 | Soil Compaction Mitigation Measures

The indicative soil compaction map devised here serves as a roadmap for managers and stakeholders, defining regions with varying compaction and helps to identify the most influential factors that increase soil compaction in different parts of Ireland. To mitigate soil compaction, it is recommended that strategies focus on management in regions with higher SMD class values, particularly in BD2 and BD3 classes, although risk still remains within the lower SMD classes.

For all regions that are characterised by heavy textures and heavy-loam textures associated with high rainfall, avoiding trafficking in wet conditions is a critical first step (Emmet-Booth et al. 2020). The right planning of field operations is essential to maintain soil structural quality efficiently, so the correct use of SMD as an indicator of soil wetness becomes an important tool to plan field operations. Farmers in these regions are encouraged to lighten the load applied in the field when trafficking, preferring the use of lighter machinery (Lepore et al. 2024; Batey 2009). Bondi et al. (2021) developed the first soil trafficking index for Ireland, which recommends avoiding trafficking pressures over 213,914 kg × year ha⁻¹ for grazing and 4412 kg × year ha⁻¹ for machinery trafficking in Ireland, above which thresholds soils are at higher risk of compaction. As such, it is important to maintain extra caution in poorly drained sites that are more susceptible to compaction (Bondi et al. 2021). If traffic is needed, it will become important to reduce the pressure on the soil through the adoption of wide tyres or dual wheels, especially during wet conditions (Emmet-Booth et al. 2020; Lepore et al. 2024; Batey 2009). Controlled traffic in all areas affected by high rainfalls and poor

or moderate drainage status is an effective strategy. This can be coupled with the use of GPS technology that is designed to ensure that machinery uses defined and permanent paths so as to avoid the traffic of the entire field and reduce the area of soil affected by repeated wheel tracks.

The south-west of Ireland presents unique challenges for soil management as the rainfall is more frequent than in the rest of the country, as is characterised by a larger window of untrafficable days. In these cases, farmers are advised to reduce the grazing season to avoid the wet periods or apply rotational grazing during high-risk times to avoid severe compaction (Lepore et al. 2024). As the stocking rates are often high in these regions, allowing fields under high livestock pressure to rest is a common practice that enables compacted soils to recover naturally over time. Buffer zones near watercourses are also essential to prevent soil runoff and protect soil structure in these vulnerable areas. This, with the integration of agroforestry including hedgerows within agricultural landscapes, can provide long-term benefits by stabilising soils and enhancing water infiltration.

Artificially improving drainage systems, such as implementing mole drainage, can play a crucial role in mitigating compaction. However, the implementation of any drainage system should be carefully considered on a site-by-site basis, as this decision requires careful evaluation. Artificial drainage can have significant implications for other soil functions, such as SOC sequestration, nutrient cycling and biodiversity enhancement, particularly in heavier soils, and such implications must be borne in mind when considering land drainage systems (O'Sullivan et al. 2015; Torres-Sallan et al. 2017). Maintaining or enhancing organic matter is essential in any soil type for improving resilience to compaction (Bondi et al. 2021). Grassland management practices, such as introducing deep-rooting species like chicory, are particularly effective. These species improve root penetration, enhance soil structure and simultaneously increase organic matter levels over time (Shaheb et al. 2021). Our results demonstrated that soils with high organic carbon levels, such as those present in the central and north-eastern regions of Ireland, exhibited greater resilience to compaction even with adverse weather regimes (BD2). This resilience highlights the ability of organic-rich soils to counteract the effects of compaction, reducing its severity.

In the east and especially south-east regions, where soils are typically free-draining, localised compaction is a common challenge due to intensive tillage and grazing systems (Lepore et al. 2024; Bondi et al. 2021). To maintain soil health and mitigate compaction risks, especially in tillage systems, farmers often adopt the use of cover crops and organic manures into their rotations (Shaheb et al. 2021). Cover crops play a dual role: they build soil organic matter and enhance soil structure whilst reducing the risk of compaction during periods when the land is not cultivated (Shaheb et al. 2021).

Mechanisation, such as ploughing or subsoiling, is considered a last-resort strategy to remediate compaction and, if employed, it should be part of a carefully planned tillage strategy. Alternating the depth of ploughing over time can help prevent the formation of plough pans, whilst subsoiling can address severe compaction

in specific cases. Furthermore, subsoiling is only effective in very dry soil conditions, where the soil can fracture properly without causing further damage. Its use should be restricted to situations where compaction is severe and other mitigation options are insufficient (Emmet-Booth et al. 2020).

4.4 | Further Climate Change Risk

The effects of climate change on soil dynamics is still a subject of relative uncertainty (Bradford et al. 2016). A review by Hamidov et al. (2018) of 20 agricultural adaptation case studies across Europe suggests that soil compaction will likely remain a serious threat under future climate change scenarios. In Ireland, compaction may be further exacerbated by projected climate changes. Nolan et al. (2017) project up to a 20% increase in heavy rainfall events during winter and autumn, whilst the frequency of extended dry periods in summer is expected to increase substantially by mid-century. The most recent decade analysed by Murphy et al. (2018) in a continuous 305-year monthly rainfall series was found to be the wettest on record, whilst multi-centennial trends of increasing winter and decreasing summer precipitation were evident. Inter-decadal precipitation variability is also thought to be much larger than previously estimated (Murphy et al. 2018). Increases in temperatures are expected under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, as modelled by Nolan and Flanagan (2020), as well as more extreme weather phenomena by mid to end of the century (Matthews et al. 2016). These future scenarios will likely influence soil moisture dynamics and the number of untrafficable days across Ireland's drainage groups. Therefore, the effect of climate change on soil compaction in Ireland must be of continuous monitoring and consideration. Addressing areas of compaction and implementing sustainable management practices in a timely manner will enhance resilience to the future impacts of climate change on soil compaction. By adopting strategies at appropriate spatial scales, the effects of increased extreme weather events and changing precipitation patterns can be mitigated.

4.5 | Limitations and Potential

The explicit aims of this paper were to assess soil compaction and to develop an Indicative National Soil Compaction Assessment map for Ireland. This map was applied to the Irish SIS, with a scale of 1:250,000, capable of accounting for variability at soil association level. When visually compared with EU soil compaction mapping efforts, such as the Natural Susceptibility to Compaction map (EC Joint Research Committee (JRC) 2008) the general trends across maps are similar. For example, areas in the west of Ireland are associated with a higher compaction risk for both maps. However, our national map at 1:250,000 resolution captures a significantly higher degree of granularity in the data. This is due to the use of higher-resolution soil data coupled with national weather datasets, enabling it to better capture regional differences within the country. In this context, our Indicative Soil Compaction map allows for regional differences within the country whilst also meeting the recommendations for pan-European cross-country comparisons. An important precaution for the use of the map presented in this paper, however, is that it should not be used for the determination of compaction at field scale. Rather,

this work is intended to enhance the understanding of the variability and of compaction at national scale, which could help support more targeted management of field operations informed by regional scale factors. Further research should seek to develop compaction mapping and support tools at more localised scales to support farm-level application measures. It is also important to note that the map generated here is a static representation to assess general trends in soil compaction rather than capturing temporal variations caused by changes in weather, land management, or seasonal dynamics. The Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive Proposal of 2023 seeks to lay down measures for monitoring and assessing soil health, and this creates an opportunity for temporal soil assessments. As soil compaction is a key threat to Irish soils (Creamer et al. 2010), this research has relevance within the context of the development of a monitoring network for soils.

In short, this map should not be relied upon for highly localised decision-making without supplementary field data. Its application should be complemented by real-time assessments of soil wetness and compaction specific to individual fields. Visual soil assessment techniques can play a crucial role in validating soil compaction on-site and, when used alongside the National Indicative Soil Compaction Map, can guide site-specific management strategies that also consider the site's historical context (Emmet-Booth et al. 2020).

5 | Conclusion

Soil compaction has been identified as a key threat to Irish soils and is significantly influenced by management regimes and weather patterns. This study aimed to assess soil compaction in Ireland through the development of the first national-level Indicative Soil Compaction map for Ireland. Compaction was particularly evident in the southwest, which may be attributed to adverse climatic and environmental conditions, characterised by poorly draining soils and above-average rainfall, combined with intensive agricultural practices. In the southeast, significant compaction was evident and likely driven by management practices only, given the favourable soil characteristics and fewer untrafficable days due to weather. High levels of mechanisation and heavy machinery use in these areas have likely altered the inherent soil structure, which is reflected in higher BD values.

Through this work, we have highlighted the variability of compaction in Ireland, providing a guide for stakeholders to support best management practices that will sustain Ireland's agricultural sector's long-term viability and resilience. The regional disparity found in Ireland for soil compaction highlights the importance of country and regional level investigations into soil threats across other EU member states. Such research should help inform appropriate management regimes and national policy shifts in line with the Green Deal and other EU-wide policies.

Author Contributions

Vajihe Shahrokh: conceptualization, methodology, writing – original draft, investigation, formal analysis, data curation, writing – review and editing. **Giulia Bondi:** conceptualization, investigation, methodology, writing – review and editing, supervision, resources, project

administration. **Alan Fahy:** methodology, validation, investigation, formal analysis, data curation, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Lilian O'Sullivan:** conceptualization, investigation, funding acquisition, supervision, resources, project administration, writing – review and editing, methodology.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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